

TREATMENT OF PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN SECONDARY TO BURN DISEASE

Haydarov M.M.

Samarkand State Medical University, Clinic Pharmacology Department.

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Abstract. *Pneumonia is a serious disease in which an inflammatory process occurs in the lungs. In children, this disease is often especially severe due to the immaturity of the respiratory system, as well as the inability to fully cough up sputum. Pathology requires mandatory prescription of antibiotics and symptomatic drugs, and in severe cases hospitalization. Experienced doctors of the children's department of SM-clinic in Moscow conduct a complete examination of a child with symptoms of pneumonia, make a diagnosis and prescribe an effective complex treatment.*

Keywords: *pneumonia, the nature of pneumonia in children, the course of pneumonia in children, the clinic of pneumonia in children.*

Pneumonia in children is seasonal. It is more common in the cold season, which occurs as a complication of influenza and other acute respiratory viral infections. Pathology requires special attention from both parents and doctors, because children are more likely to develop severe complications than adults.

Classification of pneumonia in children

There are different types of classification of pneumonia in children, each of them takes into account certain features of the development and course of the pathology. Depending on the origin, a distinction is made between hospital-acquired (the infection occurs in the hospital) and community-acquired pneumonia.

The characteristics of the course allow distinguishing acute and prolonged forms, and the cause of the development of the inflammatory process determines the following types of pneumonia in children:

- viral;
- mushroom;
- bacterial;
- mycoplasma;
- parasitism;
- chlamydia;
- mixed up

Another classification criterion is the characteristics of the X-ray image. Pulmonary involvement can be focal (small lesions), segmental (affecting a lung segment), lobar, or interstitial.

Symptoms of pneumonia in children

The difficulty in diagnosing pneumonia in children is that the initial symptoms of the disease are practically no different from the symptoms of a common cold or flu. Thus, it is difficult to distinguish the clinical presentation of the bacterial form of pneumonia from the flu. Symptoms include chills, fever, increased sweating, cough, shortness of breath, and increased heart rate. The viral form of lung disease is characterized by symptoms such as dry cough, fever, headache,

weakness and muscle pain, fatigue and loss of appetite. It should be noted that with viral pneumonia, in some cases only an increase in body temperature to sub febrile values is observed. Inflammation of the lungs caused by mycoplasmas, at the beginning of its course, is similar to the viral or bacterial form of pneumonia, but the symptoms are less pronounced. This form is characterized by a long course with severe shortness of breath and a feeling of suffocation.

Common symptoms for all forms of pneumonia:

- increased body temperature;
- cough (first dry, then with sputum);
- general weakness, drowsiness;
- Headache;
- pain in the chest area;
- shortness of breath;
- loss of appetite.

Parents should not self-medicate, but should immediately consult a doctor with their child at the slightest signs of pneumonia or other pathology of the respiratory system.

Causes of pneumonia in children

The main reason for the development of the disease is the penetration of infectious pathogens into the child's respiratory system. Usually, the child's body is able to overcome the infection on its own, preventing the development of symptoms, but when the immunity is weakened, the body cannot resist the pests, then inflammation develops in the lungs. The condition can be caused by hypothermia, vitamin deficiency, long-term antibiotic therapy, frequent contact with a sick environment, etc.

The following forms of pathogenic microflora can lead to the development of pneumonia:

- bacteria - pneumococci, streptococci, staphylococci;
- viruses - parainfluenza virus, herpes;
- yeast-like fungi;
- mycoplasma and chlamydia.

Doctors distinguish between primary pneumonia, in which the infection first appears in the respiratory system, and secondary, which is a complication of untreated acute respiratory infection.

Diagnosis of pneumonia in children

Any suspicion that a child has pneumonia is a serious reason to contact a medical institution. If there is no timely help, the patient may develop chronic bronchopulmonary diseases. During the initial examination, a pulmonologist or pediatrician carefully listens to the complaints of the patient and his parents, collects the anamnesis necessary for an objective assessment of the child's condition. Then the doctor begins the examination using instrumental diagnostic methods. First of all, the specialist listens to the child's breathing using a stethoscope - this is necessary to detect wheezing. The child's lungs are also gently tapped to determine the presence of compression in the lung tissue.

After the initial diagnosis, the small patient is sent for additional tests to confirm the assumption. In our clinic, the following laboratory and instrumental methods are used for the diagnosis of pneumonia:

- X-ray of the chest;
- general and biochemical blood test (to determine the type of infection that caused pneumonia);

sputum analysis, etc.;
EKG and cardiologist consultation;
FVD.

Based on the results of all studies, the doctor chooses the most effective treatment in each specific case.

Treatment of pneumonia

Treatment of pneumonia requires special attention from the patient's parents, because the condition of a child with pneumonia is unstable and can deteriorate at any time. In this regard, in most cases, doctors recommend hospitalizing the child and conducting the necessary therapy under the supervision of qualified specialists. The choice of treatment for pneumonia in children depends on its symptoms and cause, the stage and degree of the inflammatory process.

Eliminating the main cause of the disease, that is, bacteria, viruses or fungi that have entered the body. For this, the child is prescribed antibiotics, antiviral or antifungal drugs. At the same time, doctors carefully monitor the effectiveness of treatment and, if necessary, adjust the treatment. Eliminating the inflammatory process using antipyretic and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. Elimination of symptoms that cause discomfort to the child. Thus, mucolytic (expectorant) drugs can be prescribed for difficult sputum production, and bronchodilators for spasms of the respiratory tract.

After eliminating acute inflammation, you can use physiotherapeutic methods to treat pneumonia: electrophoresis, massage and exercise therapy.

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